

Intramolecular Hydrogen Bonding in 2-(Substituted Amino-) Methyl-4-Acetamidophenol

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Intramolecular H-bonding in the titled compounds have been detected by IR and UV. The effect of such bonding on the phenolic dissociation constant (pK_a), determined by spectrophotometric titration, provides additional support to the observed data. The hydrogen bond energy, calculated from shift in λ_{max} , roughly parallels the basicity of the parent amine on the side chain.

In connection with another work¹, attempted methylation of II² ($R = NEt_2$) either by diazomethane or alkali dimethyl sulphate combination proved to be unrewarding and the base was observed to dissolve with some difficulty in dilute alkali compared to I. These observations coupled with structural features suggested the possibility of intramolecular hydrogen bonding in II ($R = NEt_2$) and prompted us to prepare and examine the physico-chemical properties of several analogous compounds (II, $R =$ base).

In the case of *ortho*-hydroxybenzyl amines Freedman³ has already demonstrated the occurrence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding through IR; and a more recent example is found in the case of N-(2-hydroxy-3,5-dimethylbenzyl-) piperidine⁴ (III). Besides, Kappé and Armstrong⁵ have recorded the effect of such bonding on the apparent dissociation

1. P. B. Talukdar and S. K. Sengupta, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 104.
2. J. H. Burckhalter, F. H. Tendick, E. M. Jones, P. A. Jones, W. F. Holcomb and A. L. Rawlins, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1363.
3. H. H. Freedman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2900.
4. A. O. Fitton, A. Rigby and R. J. Hurlock, *J. Chem. Soc. (c)*, 1969, 230.
5. T. Kappé and M. D. Armstrong, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8**, 368.

constant (pK_a) of the *ortho*-phenolic group in structurally analogous compounds like β -(hydroxyphenyl)-ethanol amines(IV) as well as mono- and dihydroxy phenethylamines (V). They observed increased acidity (i.e., lower pK_a) of the phenolic group in some cases and the phenomenon has been attributed to increased interaction between the phenolic OH group and the side chain amine function.

In the light of these observations, we have not only measured the apparent dissociation constants (pK_a) of II, but their UV and IR data are also recorded in support of our contention.

EXPERIMENTAL

M.ps. are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded with Perkin Elmer model 21 spectrophotometer. Spectral measurements in different solvents were carried out with Hilger automatic recording spectrophotometer. Solvents were either AR grade or purified according to Vogel⁶. Most of the compounds were sparingly soluble in cyclohexane; the dimethylamino- and the pyrrolidino derivatives could not be dissolved in that solvent even under refluxing condition.

Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Titrations: pK_a values were determined by spectrophotometric titrations⁷ at 260 $m\mu$ corresponding to the phenolate ion using Hilger UVISPECK spectrophotometer and Cambridge pH meter. The results are recorded in Table I and are uncorrected for ionic strength. Conductometric titrations were performed with Philips conductivity measuring bridge using 0.01N alkali against $\sim 1 \times 10^{-3}$ molar solution of substrates.

Preparation of 2-(substituted amino-)methyl-4-acetamidophenols (II): The compounds reported in Table I were synthesized from *p*-acetylamino-phenol (I), formaldehyde (37% v/v) and appropriate secondary amine as described in the lit.³ Except the dimethylamino derivative (II, R = NMe₂), all other compounds had been previously reported either as 4-acetyl derivative or as dihydrochloride after hydrolysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to gain some qualitative experience on the relative acidities of the phenolic groups in I and II (R = base), conductometric titrations were carried out in the usual manner. But it was a surprise to observe rather well defined breaks (conductance *vs* alkali titre) in II with R = diethylamino, pyrrolidino and piperidino in contrast to ill-defined breaks I and II (R = dimethylamino and morpholino groups). These results presumably reflect the influence of sidechain base on the dissociating ability of the *ortho*-phenolic group.

However, a more quantitative picture emerges from the determination of apparent pK_a values of I and II. From the recorded data in Table II, it is clear that the observed pK_a values are in agreement with the anticipated trend from conductometric titration. Thus, diethylamino-, pyrrolidino- and piperidino derivatives of II are more acidic than I, but pK_a values of dimethylamino- and morpholino derivatives of II are comparable to that of I.

6. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1959.

7. B. Roth and J. F. Bunnett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 334.

The above indications on intramolecular hydrogen bonding^{8,9} in II were finally settled through the IR spectra by the occurrence of a wide band at about 2800 to 3300 cm^{-1} . Two typical cases are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. I. Typical IR spectra showing the occurrence of bonded OH-group in II.

In this context, detailed examination of the spectra characteristics of I and II were undertaken with solvents of varying polarity. Thus, the UV spectra of I exhibit an intense band at 249 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 13000) and a shoulder around 290 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , \sim 3000). The ratio of λ_{max} of these two bands is about 1.20; hence they could be reasonably attributed to benzenoid ¹La and ¹Lb bands¹⁰. The derivatives of I(II) show similar absorption pattern. Since the long wavelength band appears as shoulder or inflexion, subsequent work is based on the analysis of the primary band (¹La) around 250 $\text{m}\mu$. It may be mentioned here that similar UV spectral characteristics have been found by Kappé and Armstrong⁵ for β -(hydroxyphenyl) ethanolamines.

From the data in Table 2, some red shift could be noted in each case in going from water to cyclohexane or acetonitrile indicating the presence¹¹ of intramolecular H-bonding in II. Further, complete rupture¹² of this bond occurs in aqueous acid only. Any marginal effect⁹ of intermolecular association on λ_{max} arising through the breakdown of the internal bond, is almost completely suppressed in acidulated water. Moreover, the energy of such intermolecular association with solvent does not compare at all with intramolecular type¹³.

8. C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, London, 1963, 181.
9. G. C. Pimentel and A. L. McClellan, "The Hydrogen Bond", W. H. Freeman and Company, San Francisco, 1960.
10. H. H. Jaffé and M. Orchin. "Theory and Application of Ultraviolet Spectroscopy", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1964, 257.
11. H. Shingu, *Nature*, 1934, **143**, 1068.
12. J. E. Fernandez and W. I. Ferree, Jr., *Quart. Jour. Florida Acad. Sci.*, 1966, **29**, 13.
13. H. H. Szmant, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2288.

In one instance (II, R = NEt₂), λ_{max} was checked and found to be independent of concentration in cyclohexane solution. However, the weakness of the internal bonding in the case of dimethylamino- and morpholino derivatives is indicated in the spectral data in Table 2. Thus, these two compounds show slight and identical red-shift in ether and alcohol compared to that in a nonpolar solvent. But the phenomenon is not observed in three other cases, although water apparently is able to cause some fission only in the case of diethylamino derivative. Presumably, dimethylamino- and morpholino derivatives largely exist as free phenol in dilute aqueous solution and that explains their comparable pK_a's with that of I. On the other hand, increased acidities of the other three members over the parent compound (I) may be attributed, following Kappé and Armstrong⁵, to increased interaction between phenolic hydrogen and partially charged amino group. But in a nonpolar solvent these compounds largely exist as intramolecularly bonded form.

TABLE 1

Properties of p-acetylaminophenol (I) and 2-(substituted amino-)methyl-4-acetamidophenol (II)

No.	Compound	M.P., °C		pK _a (±0.05) in water at 25°	pK _b of the parent base	H-bond energy Kcal/M	Mol. Form.	N(%)	
		Found	Rept'ed					Calc.	Found
1.	I	169	168	9.35	—	—			
2.	II, R=dimethyl- amino	166-67		9.45	3.22	2.131	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	13.46	13.26
3.	II, R=diethyl- amino	134-35	135; 218-20*d	8.00	2.89	3.004	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	11.86	11.95
4.	II, R=pyrrolidino	116-17		7.90	2.88	3.229	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	11.96	11.77
5.	II, R=piperidino	158-59	153-54*	7.80	2.80	3.243	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	11.29	11.21
6.	II, R=morpholino	132-33	133; 259-60*d	9.90	9.61	2.790	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	11.20	11.34

* dihydrochloride.

On account of these findings, it is tempting to ascertain the relative strength of H-bonding in II. For such purposes, UV data have already been used¹⁴ with some success by measuring the extent of shift in λ_{max} between bonded and nonbonded forms (*o*-methylethers in the case of phenols) in the same solvent. As preparation of *o*-methylether from II was unsuccessful, we have utilised a less rigorous method to ascertain the relative strength of H-bonding in II from a knowledge that the presence of -CH₂N⁺R₁R₂H as side chain in the aromatic ring does not significantly alter the absorption pattern of the parent compound¹⁵. Thus, it is possible to get some idea of their relative strengths from the difference in shift (Δ λ_{max}) between acidulated water and cyclohexane or similar solvent (Table 2).

14. G. Gabor and E. Fischer, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 2478.

15. Ref. 10, p. 251 and 484, cf. ref. 5 and N. M. D. Brown and D. C. Nonhebel, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 5655.

TABLE 2

Special data for the primary band (¹La) of I and II.*

Solvent	I	II, R=dime- thylamino	II, R=diethyl- amino	II, R=pyrro- lidino	II, R=piperi- dino	II, R=morpho- lino
	m μ	m μ	m μ	m μ	m μ	m μ
Cyclohexane	244-45	-	252	-	252	251
Acetonitrile	-	248	252	252.5	-	-
Ether	264	249.5	-	252.5	251.5	252
Ethanol (ϵ)	249 ^a (13,090) ~288(2,000)	249.5 (17,750) ~288(2,270)	252 (12,710) ~290(2,360)	252 (12,710) ~291(2,500)	252 (12,880) ~290(2,670)	252 (13,110) ~290(2,220)
Isopropanol	250	250.5	-	253	252.5	252
Water	243.5	243.5	249	251	252	246
Water+acid	243.5	243.5	245.5	245.5	245	245.5
Water and alkali	257	258	259	260.5	260	260

* conc. $\sim 1 \times 10^{-4}$ moles/l.(a) λ_{max}^{EtOH} 250 m μ (ϵ , 13, 800) cited in The Merck Index (Merck and Co. Rahway, N.J., U.S.A.), 1960, 537.

Further, the observed pK_a values of II, were found to be linearly correlated with pK_b of the parent base in the side chain, excepting the morpholino derivative. Again, the plot of pK_a vs pK_b suggests that with the given type of compounds, H-bonding is likely to be weak when $pK_b \approx 4$ or higher. With the data in hand, this trend is of somewhat limited utility; nevertheless, the results, by and large, are in agreement with those of Freedman³ that other things remaining equal, the basicity of side chain nitrogen is the most important parameter in the formation of a H-bond.

Since piperidine and morpholine have near identical conformation, the weakness of the H-bonding in the latter could be attributed to its inherent weakness in basicity. But the observed high pK_a (9.45) of the dimethylamino derivative (II, R = NMe₂) in contrast to its closely related diethylamino derivatives (II, R = NEt₂) warrants some additional comments.

It should be appreciated that the amino function in II (R = base) is *tertiary* in character in all cases and the possibility of hydrogen bonding is more likely to be affected by steric inhibition to solvation than by any other consideration^{3,16}. Similarly, steric inhibition to

16. A. Nyquist, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1963, **19**, 1655.

solvation in influencing the acidities of a substrate has been recently reported on several occasions¹⁷. But Brown¹⁸ and others¹⁹ have pointed out that steric requirements is not synonymous with size. In other words, the situation in the immediate vicinity of the nitrogen is expected to have a more pronounced bearing on the degree of solvation. On the basis of this reasoning, the anticipated pK_a values should conform to the following decreasing order, $Me > Et > Pyrrolidino \approx Piperidino$, and the experimental results are also consistent with this expectation.

We wish to thank Mr. P. Bagchi, Research Director, for his keen interest in this work.

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Received May 14, 1969.

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18. H. C. Brown and R. L. Klimisch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 1425.
19. E. A. McCoy and L. L. McCoy, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 2354.